

WHOLISTIC ENGINEERING

FUTURE LEADERS FOSTERING POSITIVE IMPACT

ANTONY KECHA MUNERIA

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Antony Kecha Muneria

Metrocom Consultants Limited, P.O Box 27090 – 00100 Nairobi, Kenya

Email: antonykecha@gmail.com

Abstract

In today's fast-paced world, the demanding nature of the engineering profession often takes a toll on personal health and overall well-being resulting in personal health neglect or neglecting other important life aspects leading to burnout and decreased productivity; this paper delves into various methods intended for promoting holistic wellness among young engineers.

The discussed strategies encompass: creating a supportive work environment that encourages work-life balance, providing access to mental health resources/support networks, offering wellness programs geared towards fostering physical fitness as well as mental fitness, mindful practices that emphasize stress management. and most important is cultivating a culture of continuous learning and personal development beyond technical expertise plus soft skill development programs infused within engineering curricula to equip future leaders with effective problem-solving tools.

Prioritizing young engineers' holistic wellness will equip them professionally and enable them to lead fulfilling lives. Through the implementation of these strategies, we foster positive change within engineering communities and wider societies.

Key Terms: Wholistic Engineering, Holistic Wellness, Stress Management, Work-life Balance, Mental Health, Mindfulness.

1. Introduction

The increase in the prevalence of mental health concerns among young engineers over the last few years is viewed as a serious mental health crisis requiring immediate action. According to the World Health Organization as of 2021, one in five or 22.8 per cent of adults in Kenya experiences mental illness each year, but only 47.2 per cent of those individuals seek treatment [1]. It's a problem the engineering community faces, like all others, but research continues to find more reluctance on the part of engineers to seek help when experiencing such events, both as professionals and as students.

It's unsurprising that these trends carry into the workplace. Research from EqualEngineers [2], found that only 31 per cent of engineers feel included in the environment they work in, and less than a quarter of engineers would feel comfortable discussing their challenges battling depression, or financial stress with colleagues or their superiors. Beyond that, more than four out of five engineers surveyed experienced mental health issues, with as many as 25 per cent considering self-harm and substance abuse.

The engineering profession is renowned for its rigorous demands, so how do we ensure that we have a proper balance between work and life? How do we empower these future leaders so that they are able to maintain holistic wellness and that their personal growth aligns with their professional achievements?

2. Methods

To achieve sustainable, holistic wellness we need to wholistically engineer our health and well-being at work with a few tweaks to our lifestyle and work environment in which we can find and establish what works for us to play at our optimum levels. Some of the techniques we can adopt are:

2.0 Creating a Supportive Work Environment

We spend a significant amount of time at work, getting to work or thinking about work. This makes the workplace an ideal venue for supporting people to adopt healthier habits, and there is an urgent need to tackle the poor health and well-being of people at work.

According to a study published in the Journal of Human Resource Management by O. Emre & s. De Spiegeleare (2019) [3], a supportive work environment that encourages work-life balance has a direct impact on employee well-being. It reduces the risk of burnout and promotes a healthier work-life integration. It also promotes job satisfaction that improves the quality of work and productivity job satisfaction according to the journal “IZA World of Labor” by A. Clark [4].

2.1 Wellness Programs and Physical Fitness

The American Heart Association emphasizes the importance of regular physical activity in maintaining cardiovascular health. Engaging in wellness programs as written in the book “Trends in Lifestyle and Health” by L.V Kinger [5] promotes physical fitness and helps engineers reduce the risk of heart disease, obesity, and related health issues.

An article by The Harvard Health Blog [6] discusses the role of physical activity in reducing stress and improving mood. Exercise releases endorphins, which are natural stress relievers. Wellness programs that incorporate physical fitness activities, such as yoga, aerobics, or group sports, provide engineers with outlets for stress relief. Regular exercise helps them manage work-related pressures and enhances their mental well-being. It can also contribute to increased focus and creativity in problem-solving.

Dietary plays an important role in the well-being of an individual. The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) [7] highlights the significance of wellness programs in promoting healthy lifestyle choices. These programs often include educational components that encourage participants to make better dietary choices and adopt healthier habits.

2.2 Mindfulness Practices and Stress Management

Mindfulness-based Stress Reduction is a therapeutic technique in which an instructor guides participants in practices like meditation and yoga in order to reduce stress levels. According to research done by the American Psychological Association [8], MBSR is a popular method to help those with anxiety, depression, chronic pain, addiction, immune disorders, high blood pressure, and more.

Activities such as meditation and deep breathing exercises makes one emotionally resilient, enhance cognitive functions, and ability to stay calm when under pressure [9]. This comes in handy when resolving issues thereby avoiding conflicts.

2.3 Soft Skill Development and Continuous Learning

Beyond technical expertise, young engineers should also focus on developing soft skills that are crucial for effective leadership. Skills such as communication, teamwork, and problem-solving are essential for holistic growth. Integrating soft skill development programs into engineering curricula equips future leaders with the tools they need to address challenges in a well-rounded manner.

A World Economic Forum report [10], highlights these soft skills, including problem-solving and communication, are among the most sought-after skills by employers. Developing these skills is essential for career advancement. Adaptability and resilience can be cultivated through continuous learning and personal development and through this one boosts their confidence and are more satisfied with their profession, reducing the stress associated with stagnation [11].

This can be achieved through directly engaging in engineering seminars, participating in conventions, workshops, taking up new and career-related courses, and becoming part of a professional body among others which will enable knowledge sharing and transfer.

3. Results

By implementing these strategies, it is anticipated that young engineers will experience improved well-being and a higher level of job satisfaction. The incorporation of mindfulness practices and stress management techniques into their daily routine will equip them to handle the pressures of the engineering field more effectively. Moreover, the infusion of soft skill development programs into their education will enhance their problem-solving abilities and overall interpersonal effectiveness.

4. Discussions

The holistic approach to engineering education and professional development holds significant promise. The integration of wellness programs and soft skill development not only enriches the learning experience but also equips young engineers with the tools needed to excel in their careers. By promoting work-life balance, mental health support, and mindfulness practices, engineering organizations can cultivate a workforce that is not only technically proficient but also emotionally resilient.

5. Conclusions and Recommendations

The "Wholistic Engineering" approach offers a paradigm shift in engineering education and practice. It is recommended that engineering institutions collaborate with mental health professionals to establish comprehensive support systems for young engineers. Furthermore, embedding soft skill development within engineering curricula can prepare future leaders to tackle complex challenges while maintaining their well-being. By prioritizing holistic wellness, the engineering community can shape a positive and impactful future.

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